

COHESIVE

Cohesive DMP 29032019

Admin Details

Project Name: COHESIVE

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2.0

Description

Final DMP

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1. Data summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

WP1: This is a coordination WP. No data will be collected. Annual meetings will be organised and annual reports, summarizing the results obtained in the other WPs

WP2: In this WP, online guidelines are made for efficient implementation of 'risk analysis systems for new and (re)emerging zoonoses' (WP2.1). Also a decision tool to support risk assessment is developed (WP2.2). Stakeholder analyses of OH risk analysis of zoonoses in several pilot countries as well as a systems map of the current situation can be used as examples for other countries (WP2.3)

WP3: Results are mainly build on experiences (e.g. interviews, WP3.1), network contacts and expert opinions

WP4: WP4 deals with development of web applications / tools for tracing and for risk analysis. Development includes source code, and manuals, and all material developed will be published as open source. The developed tools can be used to work on tracing and risk analysis via internet.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

WP1: summaries of results and products from WP2-3-4, [pdf-format](#)

WP2:

WP2.1: raw questionnaire data are used for discussions. Output from discussions are used to develop guidelines (website). Promotion material (infographics) is available in [pdf](#). Guidelines present as [website](#)

WP2.2: Literature review (reference data in a csv format), raw questionnaire data are used in discussions. A decision tool is made and available as an interactive web [application](#).

WP2.3: Draft stakeholder analyses of OH risk analysis of zoonoses in several pilot countries as well as a systems map of the current situation from Norway are provided in [pdf format](#).

WP3: Discussions with experts and expert opinion via questionnaires and interviews are used to map and summarise qualitative information. Final outputs are a report with summarised data included within them (pdf format). Interim records will be meeting notes, interview notes and transcripts and emails. In addition to these, specific tasks will produce the following. WP3.1 Interview recordings, transcripts of interviews, results of thematic analysis of the interviews. WP3.3 Visio document containing the Q fever systems and reporting maps. WP3.5 The list of papers reviewed, the raw data extracted from these papers and the various figures compiled for the [deliverable report](#).

WP4: The type of data for WP4 is: source code and questionnaires

Will you re-use any existing data and, if so, how?

WP1: no

WP2: no

WP3: no

WP4: no

What is the origin of the data?

WP1: Results from other WPs

WP2: Questionnaire data, literature and discussions

WP3: Questionnaire data, in-depth interviews, discussions, and literature review

WP4: source code: self-produced, fetched from other open source projects; questionnaire: interested institutions

What is the expected size of the data (if known)?

WP1: very small

WP2: very small

WP3: very small

WP4: medium size

To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?

WP1: EU, EFSA, ECDC (summary of results, possibly useful for them)

WP2: The idea is that the tools developed will find a broad use among professionals in the area of (risk-assessment of) (new/re-emerging) zoonotic diseases in European member states, but can be used worldwide

WP3: The idea is that the information gathered and analysed is useful for professionals in the area of (risk-assessment of) (new/re-emerging) zoonotic diseases in European member states, but can be used world wide. In WP3.1 the raw data (interviews and transcripts) are deemed useful only for the project members (understanding the context and references made by the interviewees). The single interviews (recordings and transcripts) are not deemed to be useful for external parties. But, the results (themes identified in the thematic analysis and described in a context) may be useful for different authorities, institutes and other researchers and actors within the field of infectious diseases. From WP3.3, the overall systems maps may be valuable for those trying to understand how to map public information systems visually. It may also provide information to public policy researchers on the current systems for non-notifiable disease reporting. From WP3.5 the raw data from literature review is not deemed useful to external parties, however the deliverable report and the figures provide a useful background to the field of economic analysis to those intending to conduct these analyses in the future.

WP4: other software developers, who want to proceed. WGS researchers, who want to find out how data sharing within Europe may be done

2.1 FAIR data: Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata?

On the One Health EJP website, under outcomes an outcome inventory is present in which all products are findable, with metadata. <https://onehealthj.eu/outcome-inventory>

WP1: Yes, metadata will be provided online (i.e. title, keywords, author, subjects and others)

WP2: Yes, metadata will be provided online (i.e. title, keywords, author, subjects and others)

WP3: Yes, metadata will be provided online (i.e. title, keywords, author, subjects and others)

WP4: Open Source code and its metadata is easy to find on publicly available github, or CRAN or other to be determined publicly available platforms. Location of the above are provided in the final [report](#).

Are the data produced and/or used in the project identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism?

WP1: no

WP2: In case a product is peer reviewed published, there will be a DOI

WP3: In case a product is peer reviewed published, there will be a DOI

WP4: In case a product is peer reviewed published, there will be a DOI. There will also be a DOI for software releases, it is planned to realize that with the Zenodo platform

What naming conventions do you follow?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: n.a.

WP3: n.a.

WP4: n.a.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: In case of (peer reviewed) publication, yes

WP3: In case of (peer reviewed) publication, yes

WP4: In case of (peer reviewed) publication, yes

What is your approach for clear versioning?

WP1: Version control of the reports, to be determined per document

WP2: Version control of the reports, to be determined per document. Updates of online versions/pages will be clearly indicated.

WP3: Version control of the reports, to be determined per document

WP4: source code versioning is automatically done by the versioning system git. Software releases follow the well known semantic versioning (aka SemVer, see <https://semver.org/spec/v2.0.0.html>), currently the best known and most widely adopted version scheme in this category, uses a sequence of three digits (Major.Minor.Patch). Furthermore the versioning of releases will be done automatically by Zenodo.

What metadata will be created?

WP1: none, except metadata to help find the documents

WP2: date of creation/update, involved organisations, contact person

WP3: date of creation/update, involved organisations, contact person

WP4: typical metadata of source code development, see github. E.g. when, who, what was developed - source code line by source code line. To be determined for the questionnaire.

2.2. FAIR data: Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If some data is kept closed provide a rationale for doing so.

WP1: Depending on strategy OHEJP how to deal with annual reports

WP2: Guideline website of WP2.1 is publicly available. Risk assessment support tool is publicly available (WP2.2). Examples of stakeholder analyses and systems mapping will be publicly available (WP2.3). Raw (questionnaire) data and cleaned (questionnaire/discussion) data will not be made publically available, because lack of quality and/or not informative and/or not re-usable. Those data are only used as input for the final products.

WP3: Eventual tools/results will be made publically available. This includes the deliverable reports and raw data from tasks 3.3 and 3.5. Raw (questionnaire) data and cleaned (questionnaire/discussion) data will not be made publically available, because of confidentiality and/or not informative and/or re-usable. Those data are only used as input for the final product.

WP3.1 To enable open discussions and information retrieval the interviewees were informed that their identity would be protected within the project. Interview recordings and transcripts will not be made publicly available for confidentiality reasons as the contents of the interviews would make it easy to identify the interviewees.

WP4: produced data will to be open and accessible via links. For the questionnaire a report with aggregate data is planned.

How will the data be made accessible?

On the One Health EJP website, under outcomes an outcome inventory is present in which all products are findable, with metadata. <https://onehealthjep.eu/outcome-inventory>. In addition, all products will be findable in or via Zenodo.

WP1: see above

WP2: see above. In addition, are the guidelines available via a two unique urls (www.onehealthguidelines.eu and www.ohras.eu). The risk assessment decision support tool available via <http://cohesive.onehealthjep.eu/>. Publications are and will be accessible via Open Access journals (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100266>)

WP3: The final report, including results, will be available on the OHEJP website.

For WP3.1 In addition to the final report, a scientific publication with open access is in progress.

WP4: source code and program itself via internet - github repositorygithub, or CRAN or other to be determined publicly available platforms. (Robert.optiz@bfr.bund.de; Marion.gottschald@bfr.bund.de; A.dipasquale@izs-am.it; cohesive@rivm.nl)

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

WP1: none

WP2: For T2.2, the decision-support tool will be publicly available online, including all code and metadata, with the only requirement for use being a web browser.

WP3: Every attempt will be made to remain compatible with open access/freeware tools (such as Libre Office)

WP4: source code is accessible via browsers and git clients. The report of the questionnaire will be available online. You need a browser to access the program rrisk, Food chain lab and CIS.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation, and code be deposited? Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

WP1: no data, just reports. See under availability

WP2: Source code and related metadata for the decision support tool are deposited

WP3: For WP3.1 Raw data (i.e. interview data and transcripts) for each country will be deposited by each partner performing the interviews.

WP4:all will be deposited on github including documentation via a wiki.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

WP1: depending on OHEJP strategy. Probably only on EJP website

WP2: No restriction for final tools/products. Raw and cleaned data only accessible for project partners, stored by responsible partner. Kitty.maassen@rivm.nl; cohesive@rivm.nl

WP3: No restriction for final tools/products. Raw and cleaned data are only accessible for project partners. elina.lahti@sva.se; cohesive@rivm.nl

WP4:no restriction - internet.

2.3. FAIR data: Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable? What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: n.a.

WP3: n.a.

WP4: parts of the software will follow style guides: <https://angular.io/guide/styleguide>. The development of data structures will include standards, e.g. EFSA SSD2

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: n.a.

WP3: n.a.

WP4: n.a.

2.4. FAIR data: Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: Final products will be publically available

WP3: Final products (results) will be publically available

WP4: it is planned to publish source code on the most possible free license. At the moment the licenses are GPLv3 (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GNU_General_Public_License) and MIT (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License).

When will the data be made available for re-use? If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed.

WP1: n.a.

WP2: n.a.

WP3: n.a.

WP4: n.a.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

WP1: final products not restricted

WP2: final products not restricted

WP3:final products not restricted

WP4:not restricted.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

WP1:no end

WP2: no end

WP3: no end

WP4: no end

Are data quality assurance processes described?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: quality is assured by selecting peer reviewed journals for publication

WP3:quality is assured by selecting peer reviewed journals for publication

WP4: yes, it is described in the wiki of the github repositories how the quality of the source code is guaranteed. The workflow on how the data is automatically cleaned, individually reviewed and published is described as well.

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these costs be covered?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: costs not noteworthy

WP3: costs not noteworthy

WP4: costs hopefully not noteworthy

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

WP1: each tasks and subtasks leaders are responsible

WP2: each tasks and subtasks leaders are responsible

WP3: each tasks and subtasks leaders are responsible

WP4: each task and subtask leaders are responsible no datamanagement for rrisk / but there will be someone responsible for maintenance. Because rrsik is intended to be regularly used by BfR this service is expected to be installed.

What are the costs and potential value of long term preservation?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: costs for maintaining the website with the guidelines most likely will be covered by partners in MVNA (8.000euro/year). Potential value on a long term .

WP3: costs not noteworthy. Potential value on a long term.

WP4: costs not noteworthy. Potential value on a long term

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

WP1: n.a.

WP2: n.a.

WP3: n.a.

WP4: n.a.

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

WP1: no

WP2: no

WP3: To enable open discussions and information retrieval the interviewees were informed that their identity would be protected within the project and their consent to participate was based on these conditions. However, although not revealing names of the interviewees the interview material contains information that would make it easy to identify the interviewees. Thus, the raw data cannot be shared as this would violate the conditions for consent to participate. No such issues were identified for task 3.3 or 3.5 which use data that is already publicly available.

WP4:restrictions on the licenses needs to be followed. These licenses have very low impact on the re-use of the source code.

See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GNU_General_Public_License and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIT_License

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

WP1: no

WP2: no

WP3: no

WP4: no.